

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols by Pyridinium Fluorochromate

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Pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) has been reported as a powerful and versatile oxidant¹. However, kinetics of oxidation of secondary alcohols have not been investigated. The kinetics of oxidation of several primary alcohols by PFC have already been reported from our laboratory². It is known, however, that primary and secondary organic compounds sometimes follow different mechanistic pathways. Such examples are well known in many reactions of primary and secondary halides³. We report here the kinetics of oxidation of eight aliphatic secondary alcohols, 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol by PFC in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO).

Results and Discussion

The rate and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols investigated. Since the results are similar, only representative data are documented here.

The reactions are of first order with respect to PFC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) does not depend on the initial concentration of PFC. The reaction is of first order with respect to alcohols also (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT FOR THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY PFC AT 288 K

$10^3[\text{PFC}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$[\text{PrOH}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$[\text{TsOH}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
1.0	0.10	0.0	7.34
1.0	0.20	0.0	14.5
1.0	0.40	0.0	29.4
1.0	0.60	0.0	44.0
1.0	0.80	0.0	58.2
1.0	1.00	0.0	73.7
2.0	0.40	0.0	30.0
4.0	0.40	0.0	28.7
8.0	0.40	0.0	29.7
1.0	0.40	0.0*	29.4
1.0	0.10	0.1	12.1
1.0	0.10	0.2	16.6
1.0	0.10	0.3	21.5
1.0	0.10	0.5	32.0
1.0	0.10	0.8	45.7
1.0	0.10	1.0	55.0

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$.

The oxidation of 2-propanol, under a nitrogen atmosphere, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. The rates of oxidation of ten secondary alcohols were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters at 298 K were calculated (Table 2).

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE OXIDATION OF RCHOHM_c BY PFC

Subst.	$10^5 k$ ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)				ΔH^* kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^* $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	ΔG^* kJ mol^{-1}
	288	298	308	318 K			
Me	73.4	163	360	800	58.0±0.8	-104±3	88.9±0.7
Et	134	290	635	1400	56.9±1.0	-103±3	88.4±0.7
Pr	268	554	1200	2490	54.0±1.9	-106±3	85.8±0.7
i-Pr	466	950	1920	4110	52.5±1.2	-108±4	84.5±0.9
iso-Bu	930	1820	3660	7430	50.2±1.0	-110±3	82.9±0.8
Bu	297	621	1250	2750	53.6±1.3	-108±4	85.6±1.0
ClCH ₂	1.21	3.03	7.42	18.2	66.2±0.8	-110±3	98.7±0.7
MeOCH ₂	10.1	23.8	55.3	130	62.2±0.9	-106±3	93.6±0.7
Ph	973	1880	3640	7070	47.8±0.7	-118±2	82.8±0.6
Benzhy- drol	1030	2000	3700	7290	46.8±0.9	-121±3	82.7±0.7
Benzhy- drol- α -d	166	337	684	1390	51.4±0.8	-120±2	87.1±0.6
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	6.20	5.93	5.41	5.24			

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was studied. The oxidation of deuterated benzhydrol exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2). The oxidation of 2-propanol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of PFC and its reactions with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 at 298 K are recorded in Table 3.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and the other acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis can be attributed to a protonation of PFC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile (1),

Solvent effect: The rate constants of oxidation (k_2) in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of linear solvation energy relationship of Kamlet *et al.*⁷,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (2)$$

where π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities, α the hydrogen bond donor acidity and A_0 the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 has a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of the equation (2), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given in eqns. (3)–(6),

$$\log k_2 = -4.40 + 1.30 \pi^* + 0.20\beta + 0.06\alpha \quad (3)$$

(±0.20) (±0.16) (±0.15)

$$R^2 = 0.8053; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.42 + 1.32 (\pm 0.18) \pi^* + 0.18 (\pm 0.15) \beta \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8032; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.34$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.48 + 1.37 (\pm 0.18) \pi^* \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7838; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.64 + 0.42 (\pm 0.30) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1084; \text{sd} = 0.36; n = 18; \psi = 0.84$$

where n is the number of data points and ψ the Exner's statistical parameter⁸. Kamlet's⁷ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 81% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is poor. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It is alone accounted for *ca.* 78% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were also analysed in terms of Swain's equation⁹ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents,

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (7)$$

where A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent, B the cation-solvating power and C the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of equation (7), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$).

$$\log k_2 = 0.62 (\pm 0.08) A + 1.42 (\pm 0.06) B - 4.61 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9766; \text{sd} = 0.04; n = 19; \psi = 0.11$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.42 (\pm 0.47) A - 3.63 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0443; \text{sd} = 0.38; n = 19; \psi = 0.91$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.37 (\pm 0.12) B - 4.41 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8803; \text{sd} = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.26$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.16 \pm 0.11 (A + B) - 4.58 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8605; \text{sd} = 0.15; n = 19; \psi = 0.48$$

The rates of oxidation of 2-propanol in the different solvents show a very good correlation in Swain's equation (equation 8) with the cation-solvation power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 88% of the data. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also accounted for *ca.* 88% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 86% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4794$; $\text{sd} = 0.28$; $\Psi = 0.57$).

TABLE 3—SOLVENT EFFECT ON THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY PFC AT 298 K

Solvent	$10^3 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	Solvent	$10^3 k_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
Chloroform	28.8	Toluene	7.25
1,2-Dichloroethane	31.6	Acetophenone	29.3
Dichloromethane	30.2	Tetrahydrofuran	17.9
Dimethyl sulphoxide	73.5	t-Butyl alcohol	14.5
Acetone	24.6	1,4-Dioxane	15.9
DMF	39.8	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	7.37
Butanone	22.0	Ethyl acetate	12.6
Nitrobenzene	43.6	Carbon disulphide	4.00
Benzene	10.2	Acetic acid	20.0
Cyclohexane	1.20		

The rates of oxidation of the aliphatic alcohols failed to yield very good correlations separately with Taft's¹⁰ σ^* and E_s (equations 12 and 13). The correlation with σ^* accounts for *ca.* 93% of the data but the correlation is not acceptable by Exner's criterion⁸,

$$\log k_2 = -1.96 (\pm 0.22) \sigma^* - 2.15 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9321; \text{sd} = 0.25; n = 8; \psi = 0.20$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.49 (\pm 1.12) E_s - 2.88 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2296; \text{sd} = 0.85; n = 8; \psi = 0.77$$

The rates were, therefore, correlated in terms of the Pavelich-Taft¹¹ dual substituent-parameter,

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (14)$$

The values of the substituent constants were obtained from the literature¹². The correlations are excellent, reaction constants being negative (Table 4). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2136$) between σ^* and E_s of the eight substituents.

The negative polar reaction constant indicates an elec-

tron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant shows a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of the high ground-state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product ketone as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results.

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION CONSTANTS

T K	ρ^*	δ	r^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.96 ± 0.01	-0.93 ± 0.02	0.998 9	0.02	0.02
298	-1.89 ± 0.02	-0.87 ± 0.03	0.996 9	0.03	0.05
308	-1.84 ± 0.01	-0.83 ± 0.02	0.999 8	0.01	0.01
318	-1.79 ± 0.03	-0.80 ± 0.04	0.997 8	0.03	0.04

The faster oxidations of 1-phenylethanol and benzhydrol may well be due to stabilization of the electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state by phenyl groups by resonance.

There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate complex in the present reaction, however, its formation in small amounts can not be ruled out. In our earlier studies of primary alcohols by PFC^{2,4}, we observed Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the reductant and suggested the formation of a chromate ester as an intermediate. It is proposed that in the present reaction also a chromate ester is formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium but the equilibrium constant is very small. The reason for this seems to be entirely steric. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 6.20$ at 288 K), confirms that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicates that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence, transfer of a hydride-ion from the alcohol to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride-ion transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents. The transfer of a hydride ion via an ester intermediate is supported by the dependence of kinetic isotope effect on temperature also. The data for protio- and deuterio-benzhydrols, fitted to the familiar expression: $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D e^{-\Delta H^*/RT}$, show a direct correspondence^{13,14} with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which activation energy difference for protio and deuterio compounds is equal to the difference in the zero-point energy for the respective C-H and C-D bonds ($\approx 4.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are almost equal. Bordwell¹⁵ gave very cogent evidences against the occurrence of concerted one-step biomolecular processes by

hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present reaction also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. The only truly symmetrical processes involving linear transfer of hydrogen are intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions characterised by transfer with cyclic transition states¹⁶. Littler¹⁷ also showed that a cyclic hydride transfer in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. The mechanism shown in Scheme 1 accounts for the observed data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the alcohols (commercial product, Fluka) were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionated. Benzhydrol was recrystallized from ethanol. PFC was prepared by reported method¹. Benzhydrol- α -d (PhCDOHPh) was prepared by the reported method¹⁸. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its nmr spectra, was $94 \pm 5\%$. Due to non-aqueous nature of the medium, *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the usual methods.

Product analysis: The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions, i.e. with an excess of the alcohol

over PFC. In a typical experiment, 2-propanol (0.05 mol) and PFC (0.01 mol) were made up to 100 ml in DMSO and kept in dark for ~10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl (2 mol dm⁻³) and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) was dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.17 g (91%) and 1.92 g (79%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with the DNP of acetone. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also.

The overall reaction may, therefore be written as

Kinetic measurements : Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the alcohol ($\times 15$ or more) over PFC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed, upto 80% reaction, by monitoring the decrease in [PFC] at 356 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}), were computed from linear ($r > 0.990$) least-squares plots of $\log [PFC]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constants, (k_2) were evaluated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{obs}/[\text{alcohol}]$.

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